

COMMUNITY CHALLENGES: SOCIAL REPRESENTATION OF SERVICE DELIVERY GIVEN BY BARANGAY OFFICIALS IN A 6TH CLASS MUNICIPALITY

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to collectively construct the meaning of the social word 'service delivery' of LGU/Barangay (Village), another is to come up with the suggested programs needed by the social group specifically the community and also to provide new knowledge to improve the service delivery of barangays. The study utilized social representation method, a way to get the opinions barangay officials and feedback of community leaders or common people in which it will "ensemble the thoughts and feelings being expressed in verbal and overt behavior of actors which constitutes an object for a social group" (Wagner et al., 1999). Purposive sampling is used to identify participants that are likely to have same experiences and focuses in small group of people (Nikolopoulou, 2023) Thus, the selection of participants fits in the study, residing in their jurisdiction. In Study 1, Analysis of Journals and articles of Service Delivery among LGU Barangays in which 75 journals were extracted from the internet for the word barangay 'service delivery' provided that barangay service delivery are fared well in providing services, Barangay service delivery establishes a council for disaster preparedness, and Barangay service delivery is monitored at all times. In Study 2 that involves interviews or an in-depth picture of 'service delivery' from LGU Barangays. Study conducted interviews for more than 25 participants from every 6th Class Municipalities (San Sebastian and Talalora, Samar. Unavailability of Infrastructure facilities such as health centers, satellite/public market, botika, post-harvest facilities, and livelihood center. Office Desks for facilitating services are less prioritized like the person with disability desk and kasambahay desk. Barangay transactions are less implemented are microbusiness registries and assistance to cooperatives/enterprises and they are not particular in updated kasambahay service transaction. Recording and documentation service transactions of barangays specifically in community beautification, updated kasambahay, recording and filing for the issuance

of cedula, and microbusiness records are less practiced. Thematic analysis revealed the three (3) story of 'service delivery' the following are: (1) They give support in teaching livelihood; (2) They provides incentives for families; (3) BSD is good and greatly appreciated. Thematic Analysis for Improvement of "Service Delivery", the following are: (1) They must provide business livelihood training and guidance for association registration (2) They must address problems of weak enforcement and awareness of solid waste management and lack of material recovery facility; (3) They must focus on the lack of facilities for providing of good service delivery; (4) They must have health facility or station with trained barangay health worker and provision of medicines.

Keywords: *Service Delivery, Social Group, Social Representation, Community, Governance, Incentives, Microbusiness, Livelihood, Facilities, Solid Waste, Health, Enforcement, Village*

INTRODUCTION

Influentially important in Local Governance is the public management, may it be informal networks and social capital that can be transformed into participation of the community, either they be encouraged or prevents them. Participation process is a venue for service relating issues on how the community is affected from the service delivery given by the Local Government, considering the policy cycle which involves policy option considerations and agenda. Public managers must make sure that participation of community is extended and sustained as the times goes by (Lowndes et al., 2001). According to Odalonu (2017) People at the grassroots serves as the key element as the government exist. Public officials like the government council serves the publics for the interest of having primary delivery of service and giving quality of life that targets the basic needs of the community and public managers and they must look at the provision on economic and social life making it as a bridge to the progress of inhabitants in in the locality by providing opportunities and development.

Objectives:

- To collectively construct the meaning of the social word 'service delivery' of LGU Barangay (Village)
- To come up with the process constructed by the social group specifically the community.
- The result can be an avenue to provide new knowledge to improve the service delivery of Barangay (Village)

Service delivery entails satisfaction, public activity policy and benefits of the community. Provisions involve goods that can be seen and service that can be satisfied by the public (Johannison, 2007). Some local government units prioritize essential needs and provide economic activities.

According to Mokalane et al. (2014), the LGU or municipality is responsible for the provision, maintenance and improvement of existing infrastructure, and the extension of services ranging from electricity and water delivery to local public transport, slaughterhouses, libraries and fire-fighting services. It was also suggested by the same researchers that municipalities must have an Integrated Development Plan (IDP) to attain success and goal achievement in the local municipality. Avis (2016) also emphasized that to ensure service delivery given to the community, health and well-being, articulate the needs of the poor by making their voice be heard, discuss the simplification by guiding them understand the regulations set by the authorities and responsiveness of the government to provide water, sanitation and management of waste or even housing. Venter (2010) suggests that LGUs should be encouraged to develop of community by improving service delivery addressing challenges and coordinately and proactively put into action in order to benefit the citizens.

Increasing functions of barangay, challenged emerge when it is has fund constraints and incapacitated especially projects for implementations. Eventually delivery services sweeps its performance either satisfactory or unsatisfactory to the community depending on the resources the barangay have. To enable to target service delivery of barangay within the 6th class municipality, interviews of barangay and community were conducted. Barangays consecutively provide specific service delivery to connect them to the response of the community that they served. In relation to the study of Montes et al. (2020), there is a incompatibility between work services expected from barangay officials and the present work they are in.

Research Questions

The study provides answers to these following questions:

1. What are the service deliveries provided by the LGU Barangay (Village)?
2. What is the story of service delivery being provided by the LGU or Barangay (Village)?
3. What do you think should be done to improve it further?
4. Who do you think is responsible to implement those changes?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study will utilize social representation method and theory to get the opinions barangay officials and feedback of community leaders or common people in which it will "ensemble the thoughts and feelings being expressed in verbal and overt behavior of actors which constitutes an object for a social group" according to Wagner et al. (1999) depicting what the community will show what service delivery of LGUs in the province socially represented as a whole. The study will also use qualitative method of research by using one-on-one interview with regards to service delivery, applying questions suits

to their vernacular. The interviews will be recorded and transcribed with consent and will use thematic analysis.

The social representation theory provides a new way in exploring LGU service delivery issues and gives an open access to the public's cognitive shared concentrating about the matters about service provided by the LGU and the leaders within the municipality from the members of the community (Moscovici, 1988). SRT may be used as it is the most effective and efficient approach because of the present collective social knowledge (Lahlou, 2001).

Social Representation Theory targets the understanding of relevant societal issues and concern such as service delivery given by the LGU Barangay (Village) within the municipality. The study will employ emancipated representation in which there will be different groups but matches one another's viewpoints (Moscovichi, 1988). In group interactions and representations livelihood and service provisions to the community stories as a tailing spill that could create a stir of concerns by the community as a challenge for them. Results and ideas came from journals, articles and media will be one of the bases in acquiring societal issues in which they struggle to bring their point of views and this will be a public pressures floats (Jovchelovitch, 2001) and according to Philogene and Deaux (2001) some problems might be seen and discovered. With this collective sharing, social representation will be developed. By this integration of experiences and knowledge that was happened before, the process will be transformed as object representation (Gaskell, 2001). Nevertheless, social representation is not only a product of shared knowledge; it is also a picture of group-constructed reality. Wagner et al. (1999) also emphasizes that people constructively collect the meaning of any social object and they attach traits and importance which makes an object part of the societal world and this theory will allow researchers capture the social groups' complexity world-making and meaning-making (Joffe, 2003) and it also can be explained in conditions surrounding an event or situation, shared beliefs, customs, norms practices and values (Baquiano and Montiel, 2011). The study will apprehend social meanings of service delivery provided by the LGU Barangay in a 6th class municipality, two strategies will be utilized: article/media analysis and interviews.

Instrumentation

The study will have these following steps:

Study 1 Analysis of Journals and articles of Service Delivery among LGU Barangays

Study 1 will examine social representation articles and journals and collected in the internet that will be validated by social representation expert and the journals will be analyzed the using thematic analysis by the researchers and validated by the evaluators.

Study 2 Interviews: An in-depth picture

Study 2 examines social representation of individual minds of the community regarding service delivery of the LGU barangays by conducting interview recorded and transcribed with consent and will also use thematic analysis.

Locale of the Study

The participant-respondent are located from the two (2) 6th Class Municipality of Samar which are San Sebastian and Talalora, Samar, Philippines. They consist of common people from people organizations (leaders and members), fisher folks, farmers, market vendors, household members and others. Sampling Procedure

The research will find and analyze 75 journals and media/articles or depending on number of which the veracity of information to be taken in relation with service delivery of LGU/barangay published in previous years and recently. The study will also conduct interviews for 15-20 participants from San Sebastian, Samar and another 15-20 participants from Talalora, Samar depending on the saturation level of the data gathered. Goulding (1999) expounded that when data saturation is used, theory/model is only considered valid when it reaches to the point of saturation.

Inclusions in the selection of participants are the common people residing in their jurisdiction that primarily provided delivery of service from the LGU Barangays. Common people can be considered as leaders in people organizations, fisherfolks, farmers, market vendors and others, regardless of their gender as much as they are given or benefited for the service of LGU Barangays.

Purposive sampling is used when units are selected in purpose with the same characteristic (Nikolopoulou, 2023) whereby delivery of service is constituted and in a form of non-probability sampling.

To validate the actual service delivery provided, the researcher also interviewed five (5) barangay officials in San Sebastian, Samar and five (5) barangay officials from Talalora, Samar.

Validation of Instrument

Interview guide and questions was validated by a social representation expert a dry-run were done in certain barangay wherein applicability of service delivery are the same targets as the sample. The team also translated the question in the language wherein they fit according to what is used in their locality which is waray-waray dialect.

Data Gathering Procedures

The first study will be sourced out media platforms, published research articles and journals as to service delivery of LGUs (Municipality/Barangay). Issues and concerns of community that needs to be addressed properly by the government. Thematic analysis will be used in securing themes that are relevant for the study.

For qualitative approach, interview guide questions are constructed in a simple manner based on the objectives which will answer the research study about service delivery. Participants will be informed about the time requirement of about more or less 30 minutes, the confidentiality of data, why they qualify to be a participant, the anonymity and privacy and lastly, the disposal of recorded session. Respondents' answers will be analyzed through thematic analysis in order to provide specific themes about service delivery as a challenging mark for the community. Validation of themes generated will also be validated by an expert.

Ethical Considerations

Conduct of the study will emphasize the confidentiality of information and details especially the critical ones. The languages used were clearly instructed to the respondents. In the qualitative methods of gathering data, in-depth interviews with the respondents will initiate in a form of invitation that includes clear description if they like to be interviewed as consent for the recording, stating also the rights and expected time finished, the current study, and the purpose. The participants are fully informed that they may have an option to voluntarily participate or withdraw their participation, Utmost privacy to protect the rights of the respondents during in-depth interview and survey were implemented.

Consent from the participating Barangay Officials and Community participants are established before the start of the data gathering procedures considering the respondents are coded for compliance of the data privacy act. The data results are deleted after utilization, analysis, and implementation and solely used for the purpose of the study.

Scope and Delimitations

This study explored the actual experience of the basic service delivery given by their Barangays with the 6th Class Municipality. The study limits from the extracting knowledge gained from their experiences and information from Barangays regarding mandated programs, facilities, projects which lead to satisfaction of residents within their jurisdiction.

RESULTS

Table 1. Infrastructure Facilities of Barangays in a 6th Class Municipalities in Samar
Barangays in San Sebastian and Talalora, Samar)

Barangay Infrastructure Service Facilities (6th Class) <i>(LGC Sec. 17 and BGPMS)</i>	Available Infra Service Facilities in Barangays (10 Barangays)	% of Infra Services Facilities Available (10 Barangays)
Bagsakan	1	10%
Health Center	0	0%
Daycare Center	2	20%
Water	9	90%
Multi-Purpose Hall	1	10%
Information Center	3	30%
Satellite/Public Market	0	0%
Botika	0	0%
Communal Garden	10	100%
Farm to Market Roads	4	40%
Material Recovery Facility	1	10%
Post-Harvest Facilities	0	0%
Evacuation Center	2	20%
Livelihood Center	0	0%
Total	33	
Percentage	24%	

**Barangays must have 14 Infra Facilities as mandated in the Local Government Code*

Table 2. Barangay Service Desk present in Barangays in a 6th Class Municipality

Barangay Service Desks (6th Class) <i>(LGC Sec. 17 and BGPMS)</i>	Available Service Desks in Barangays (10 Barangays)	% of Service Desks Available (10 Barangays)
Public Information Desk	5	50%
Lupon Tagapamayapa Desk	6	60%
VAWC Desk	8	80%
PWD Desk	3	30%
Kasambahay Desk	3	30%
Total	25	
Percentage	50%	

**Barangays must have 5 Barangay Desks as mandated in the Local Government Code*

Table 3. Barangay Services Transaction of Barangays in a 6th Class Municipality

Barangay Services Transactions (6th Class) <i>(RA 9262, RA 9003, RA 9178, RA 10361)</i>	No. of Barangays that Practice Service Availability (10 Barangays)	% of Barangays that Practice Service Availability (10 Barangays)
Issuance of Certification	10	100%
Health and Nutrition	6	60%
Resolving Disputes	10	100%
Community Law Enforcement	6	60%
Road Maintenance	10	100%
Assemblies and Consultations	10	100%
VAWC cases	9	90%
Issuance of Cedula	10	100%
Community Beautification	6	60%
Microbusiness (Registries)	5	50%
Agricultural Support	6	60%
Updated Kasambahay	3	30%
Assistance in Cooperatives/Enterprises	5	50%
Total	96	
Percentage	73.85%	

**Barangays must have 13 Barangay Services/Transactions as mandated RA 9262, 9003, 9178, 10361*

Table 4. Barangay Services Transaction Documentation of Barangays in a 6th Class Municipality

Barangay Services Transactions (6th Class) <i>(RA 9262, RA 9003, RA 9178, RA 10361)</i>	No. of Barangays that Practice Service Document Recording & Filing (10 Barangays)	% of Barangays that Practice Service Document Recording & Filing (10 Barangays)
Issuance of Certification	4	40%
Health and Nutrition	6	60%
Resolving Disputes	10	60%
Community Law Enforcement	10	100%
Road Maintenance	10	100%
Assemblée and Consultations	10	100%
VAWC cases	8	80%
Issuance of Cedula	6	60%
Community Beautification	3	30%
Microbusiness (Registries)	4	40%

Agricultural Support	6	60%
Updated Kasambahay Assistance in Cooperative/Enterprises	3	30%
	9	90%
Total	89	
Percentage	68.46%	

*Barangays must have 13 Barangay Services/Transactions as mandated RA 9262, 9003, 9178, 10361

Figure 1. Thematic Analysis of Barangay “Service Delivery” Story from the Community

Figure 2. Thematic Analysis of Barangay “Service Delivery” Suggested Improvement from the Community

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, Infrastructure Service Facilities of Barangays in 6th Class Municipalities are only 24%, this implies that lack of facilities is still a problem in Barangays to enable them to provide services. Thus, The following specific Infra facility unavailability like Health Centers, Sattelite/Public Market, Botika, Post-Harvest Facilities, and Livelihood Centers resulted in 0%.

Residents also identified some Desks (shown in Table 2) are available in their Barangay Halls, but some desks are less prioritized like the Person with Disability Desk and Kasambahay Desk with a percentage of 30% or 3 Barangays only made this possible. 8 of the Barangays out of 10 have a VAWC Desk, so there might be an implication that there are cases of VAWC within the barangay. VAWC is crucial for problems encountered by small groups of society (Consignado, 2022)

Table 3 depicted that most barangays provide services as they are expected to served showing 73.85% of the barangays successfully implemented and practice service delivery among the answers of the residents. In the laws provided, barangays must have complete services as it mandates them to do so. It has also shown that Delivery Services are not fully implemented in some barangays of a 6th Class Municipality, such as Health and

Nutrition, Community Law Enforcement, Community Beautification, and Agricultural Support has only have 60% Implementation and Practice. Next is, Microbusiness Registries and Assistance to Cooperatives/Enterprises which garnered 50% Implemented and Practiced, Lastly, barangays are not particular in Updated Kasambahay Service Transaction which rated for only 30%. Barangay Officials must implement these services as mandated by the law to fully serve the public.

Programs about health and nutrition remain a challenge in barangays as found out in the study of Garcia (1982). Barangays need a partner agency (government or private) according to Alarte (2022) to enable to guide them in the ways to sustainable livelihood activities, especially to agricultural support. Maximization of information and awareness of the Barangay Micro Business Act and other laws related to it (Balaria, 2020). Barangay Law Enforcement is least prioritized because of factors like lack of resources and training was revealed in the study by Sumad-on (2020) and agreed by Layug (2020) that it is not often given funds through the particular service criteria.

It was also further shown in the study of Layug (2010) that there is a mismatch of funding and financial capabilities of barangay that is least prioritize which is the personal services that lead to lesser funds allotted in the beautification of community barangay.

By most all means, Barangay Document recording and filing are the most reliable form of services in barangays and are often neglected as shown above table (Table 4) with a percentage of 68.46 which is considered as least practice in a 6th Class Municipalities. 4 barangay services transactions was less taken up through recording and documentation filing by some barangays specifically 30% in Community Beautification, 30% in Updated Kasambahay, 40% recording and filing for the issuance of cedula, 40% Microbusiness records.

Records Management provides timely and efficient decision-making as it promotes participation from the public and is important to future information. It also contributes effective management towards the provision of delivery services to communities, its orderly and efficient flow that performance functions can be successful (Kanzi, 2010), it is also further agreed that without records barangay or office cannot operate in formulating policies, planning activities and decision-based programs for the community.

Thematic Analysis: Social Representation of “Service Delivery” of Barangays (Villages) in a 6th Class Municipality)

The Question was given to the barangay community respondents in a 6th Class Municipality

What is the story of service delivery being provided by the LGU or Barangay?

Thematic analysis of Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ saturated three (3) representations from the societal interviews as show in the Figure 1.

Theme 1. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ Gives Support in Teaching Livelihood

Community and residents give their story that barangay ‘service delivery’ supports teaching business, financial management, and livelihood for them to become independent. Barangays must continue it support constituents and teach them how to be entrepreneurial as Alarte (2022) accentuated that there is a real need for a livelihood program in every barangay and encourages partnerships with LGUs and other agencies that would give them support. Support must also be revitalizing projects in livelihood and must focus on providing facilities and resources like financial support at the beginning sustaining its business endeavor and sustaining its community livelihood in a lifetime (Fernandez, 2019).

Theme 2. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ Provides Incentives for Families

Society came up with a notion about ‘service delivery’ of barangay, that it provides incentives for families in every household as a support for them to be encouraged to be productive among themselves. A potent solution expounded by Layug (2010), is that incentive plays a part in increasing community revenues and creativity. In fact, Pasuelo (2019). 4Ps or Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program becomes a streamlined motivation among communities, attending different assemblies, meetings, and consultations.

Theme 3. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ is Good and Greatly Appreciated

As extracted from the residents, they are satisfied with the ‘services delivery’ provided by the barangay. As it represents good and greatly appreciated for customer satisfaction, especially community-based services and it is important to assess resident’s overall satisfaction because it is essential for a barangay to serve the public (Sirgy, 2000).

Thematic Analysis: Social Representation for Improvement of “Service Delivery” of Barangays (Villages) in a 6th Class Municipality

Interviews were conducted with the community representatives and leader of which the question was asked to them for representation **“What do you think should be done to improve it further (Barangay Service Delivery)?”**

Barangay Communities were interviewed and there were four (4) themes emerged when it comes to the improvement of barangay ‘service delivery’ expectations hopefully their voices will also be heard as they consist of the bottom small group society that needs the support for the provision of knowledge and technology as possible as it may be.

Theme 1. Barangay must provide Business Livelihood Training and Guidance for Association Registration

Livelihood is a need by the barangay community and residents in a class municipality and it can be a basis for designing extension programs (Moralista et al., 2023), they lobbied this in the interview conducted by the researchers that businesses or associations also

need financial management training and workshops and it was confirmed in the study of Pamungkas et al. (2023) that there will be a positive impact if barangays would be given this type of training. Revitalization of Livelihood projects needs to be prioritized.

The Barangay community also needs support and guidance on how to register with the government to be able to be an association.

Theme 2. Barangay must address Problems of Weak Enforcement and Awareness of Solid Waste Management and Lack of Material Recovery Facility

Solid Waste Management is somewhat challenging especially to barangays as waste accumulates over time. Rao (2020) indicated that the public must still be aware and participate especially in how to dispose of waste properly. A study was also conducted by Irene (2014) but even barangays are well aware of waste management inefficiency, that is why communities are not engaging due to the fact, that it community does not know the advantages of doing waste segregation or management. While it is true that barangay or community leaders experience difficulties in enforcing solid waste management which leads to problematic results (Go, 2022), it is greatly encouraged for a stronger implementation of policies or ordinances in a barangay. The establishment of a Material Recovery Facility is recommended for a solid waste management program to be sustainable (Almazan and Vargaz, 2016).

Theme 3. Barangay must focus on the Lack of Facilities for providing Good Service Delivery

To enable a barangay office to function it is essential that resources must be present especially facilities within, one of the suggestions and opinions given was the lack of facility along post-harvest facilities for their crops and even fish and it was confirmed by Aquino-Nuevo and Ramir (2010) that to achieve efficient development, barangay must provide facilities for the people as a form of government support.

Along with evacuation facilities, the community also urges to have a safe and available place in terms of hazards and disasters and according to Vilorio (2012), there is a major consequence of unpreparedness of a barangay if infrastructures and facilities are unavailable and community services might not serve its purpose.

Theme 4. Barangay must have a Health Facility or Station with Trained Barangay Health Workers and Provision of Medicines

The last theme that emerges from among community barangays in a 6th class municipality is there must be a health facility present ideally in barangays for first aid and services specifically health within the range of location and it was identified by Wahyunugroho (2020) identifies that health facilities is a major unmet needs of the community. Such a significant issue for far-flung areas since it was also enumerated by Collado (2019) and Dagohoy (2021) the challenges along with the lack of medicines, and primary healthcare are the things to be considered by the barangays.

Barangay must also have trained Barangay health workers to increase the trust of the community and deliver what is expected from them. BHW has no place and is not fully equipped with paraphernalia for service delivery (Ibo, 2020). Another emphasis by Aytona (2021) is that there is a need to optimize BHW and primary care facilities.

The Last question was asked from the community **“Who do they think is responsible to implement those changes?”**

The community reliably answered two (2) responsible for the implementation of service delivery the data shows that out of 34 responses, 18 (52.9%) respondents say both Barangay Officials and the Community have responsibility for implementation and improvement, 12 (35.3%) answered that Barangay Officials are solely responsible barangay service delivery, 4 (11.8%) says that community has a responsibility, and the rest abstained from answering. The interview ended in every barangay. The following details are the narratives of the respondents:

Barangay Officials. They must be the one who serves the community in their utmost service and has an initiative to make facilities and services available to the community and guide them in every way where they become more productive as they fight the challenges of poverty, and dependency by introducing livelihood activities such as farming, fishing and value addition as they pursue their dreams and give their family food for their tables. Sustain through financial activities and wise spending, having community-based entrepreneurial and business activities that would suit the resources within their landscape.

Creating, reiteration of ordinance, and implementing it, major responsibilities of barangay officials for they are the ones who are considered leaders of the community. Healthcare centers, available trained health practitioners, and provision of medicines are also included in the clamors of the citizens, for hospitals are so far from the municipalities making them inaccessible for them.

Barangay community or residents. Cooperation and law-abiding citizens are expected to synergize programs, training, barangay services, and other support services that can lead them to a sustainable community and lift their status in the poverty line and the class level of the municipality.

Conclusions

The story of service delivery of barangays that are socially represented by the community opened up more room for improvement in a 6th-class municipality that should be done by every 6th-class municipality, this will bring another milestone to places where services are challenged through some lack of knowledge and technology and even facilities.

Basic barangay ‘service delivery’ in a 6th class municipality, it was validated that facilities like Health Centers, Public/Satellite Markets, Post-harvest facilities, and livelihood centers are not available in barangay within the municipality, it was also qualified in the

interview that lack of facilities and lack of training along livelihood and entrepreneurship, business and financial management among the community to become productive. Another is the health area where medicines or botika ng bayan are not available and the same as the demand for trained health practitioners or BHW.

Some Barangay Desks are not also available like Kasambahay Desk and PWD Desk which can cater to needy people because they are financially challenged and physically challenged which makes them a priority and gives them, rights awareness and privileges, concerns, and complaints of abuse.

Filing and documentation barangays are not well-maintained like 30% in Community Beautification records, 30% in Updated Kasambahay records, 40% recording and filing for the issuance of cedula, and 40% in Microbusiness records.

Thematic analysis resulted via Social Representation along “Service Delivery” of Barangays in a 6th Class Municipality are the following:

1. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ gives Support in Teaching Livelihood.
2. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ provides Incentives for Families.
3. Barangay ‘Service Delivery’ is Good and Greatly Appreciated.

Thematic Analysis via Social Representation for Improvement of “Service Delivery” of Barangays in a 6th Class Municipality are the following:

1. Barangay must provide Business Livelihood Training and Guidance for Association Registration.
 2. Barangay must address Problems of Weak Enforcement and Awareness of Solid Waste Management and Lack of Material Recovery Facility.
 3. Barangay must focus on the Lack of Facilities for providing of Good Service Delivery.
 4. Barangay must have Health Facility or Station with Trained Barangay Health Worker and Provision of Medicines.
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Recommendations

Findings from the research may become a forefront for extension proposal, projects and activities whereby results are given in which needed by the community. Future

researchers can also validate the claims from the research and recommended for further studies to address community problems especially barangays.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher acquired approved certificate compliance for ethical standard before implementation of data gathering from the Institutional Research Ethics Committee.

They are also acknowledged the different sources of information from confidential interview data every study and literatures.

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